

HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019
RM 14: MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN MIDWIFERY: RMD 321
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Mrs B.C. is a Senior Nurse Manager at St. Pauls's Hospital in the Western Region. She has 12 nurses in her team and she is the team leader in her Department and a Management Member of the Hospital. The relationship between Mrs. B.C. and the nurses is cordial and team members are often highly engaged in projects and decision - making process leading to high productivity and job satisfaction.

- a. What leadership style is Mrs. B. C. applying in her work situation? - 2 marks
- b. Mention 5 other leadership styles apart from the style applied by Mrs. B.C. - 5 marks
- c. Mention 3 disadvantages of the leadership style applied by Mrs. B.C. - 5 marks
- d. Briefly explain the differences between Management and Administration - 8 marks

QUESTION TWO

As a Midwife, you recently took over a new role as the Manager of Maternity Ward. With a high level of commitment and motivation though new in the hospital, you ensure that processes and procedures and other resources are used in an efficient and effective manner. The ward has a bed capacity of 24 with 7 newly posted midwives.

Describe Ward Management under the following:

- a. Management of newly posted midwives - 5 marks
- b. Management of client care - 5 marks
- c. Management of the environment - 5 marks
- d. Management of supplies and equipment - 5 marks

QUESTION THREE

Store Allocated Ledger

Date	Voucher No	Particulars	Received	Issued	Balance in Stock	Unit Price	Amt.

Store Receipt Voucher No. 0010

Date	Voucher No	Received From	Qty.	Description Of Good	Price	Amount	Ledger Number/ Folio	Remarks
22/05/19	00015	RM 14 Pharma	5000	Amoxycillin 250mg	0.75	3750.00	15D	Good

Date: 24/05/19

Store Keeper *[Signature]*

Requisition Book

Emergency Ward Requisition No. 518 date 27/05/19

Females Ward Requisition No. 243 date 27/05/19

Males Ward Requisition No. 630 date 27/05/19

The above Wards requested for 1500 Amoxycillin Capsules of 250mg each on this dates.

Task

1. Copy and complete the store allocated ledger. - 5 marks
2. Issue to the request of the Emergency Ward. - 5 marks
3. Grant the request of the Female Ward. - 5 marks
4. Attend to the request of the Male Ward lessen/ lesser by 100 capsules - 5 marks

QUESTION FOUR

Heal the world enterprise maintains a petty cash book for the month of May 2019 in relation to the following petty transaction. On 1st May, 2019 a cash float GHS 1,600.00 was given and the following payments were effected.

GHS

May 2: Postage stamps purchased	100	
May 3: Wages for errand boy	200	
May 5: Cost of registered letters	240	
May 6: Stationery	200	
May 7: Stamps pad	160	
May 10: Cleaning		100
May 12: Wages		200
May 14: Bought Arc files	120	
May 18: Paid for omo	70	
May 19: Casual labour	200	
May 20: Carbon papers		80
May 25: Stamp pad ink	40	
May 27: Washing powder	80	
May 30: fees for post office box	160	

Required: Prepare a petty cash book

- 20 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HOLY FAMILY NURSING AND MIDWIFERY TRAINING COLLEGE – BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY, 2019

PBM1 : MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN MIDWIFERY: RMP221

TIME ALLOWED: 1:30MINS

ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

QUESTION ONE

Mrs Adamu is a Senior Midwife at Ridge Hospital in the Western Region and head of her department. Last year, she won an award for her department as a result of proper planning.

- a. Define planning - 2 marks
- b. Enumerate 5 importance of planning - 5 marks
- c. State **five (5)** characteristics of a good leader - 5 marks
- d. As a Midwife and head of your department how can you apply the principles of time management for quality health care - 8 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

QUESTION TWO

Store Allocated Ledger

Date	Voucher No	Particulars	Received	Issued	Balance in Stock	Unit Price	Amt.

Store Receipt Voucher No. 0010

Date	Voucher No	Received From	Qty.	Description Of Good	Price	Amount	Ledger Number / Folio	Remarks
22/05/19	00015	RM 14 Pharma	5000	Amoxycillin 250mg	0.75	3750.00	15D	Good

Date: 24/05/19

Store Keeper

Requisition Book

Emergency Ward Requisition No. 518 date 27/05/19

Females Ward Requisition No. 243 date 27/05/19

Males Ward Requisition No. 630 date 27/05/19

The above Wards requested for 1500 Amoxycillin Capsules of 250mg each on this dates.

Task

1. Copy and complete the store allocated ledger. - 5 marks
2. Issue to the request of the Emergency Ward. - 5 marks
3. Grant the request of the Female Ward. - 5 marks
4. Attend to the request of the Male Ward lessen/ lesser by 100 capsules - 5 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

QUESTION THREE

Papa Garo maintains a petty cash book for the month of April 2019 in relation to the following petty transaction. On 1st April, 2019 a cash float GHS 1,000.00 was given and the following payments were effected.

	GH¢
April 4: Travelling expenses	108
April 5: Postage stamps	84
April 5: Napkins	85
April 7: Taxi fare	88
April 8: Duplicating sheets	100
April 8: Petrol	85
April 11: Envelops	164
April 13: Postage Stamps	36
April 14: Soap for Cleaning	59
April 15: Taxi fare	241
April 18: Napkins	109
April 18: Petrol	185
April 20: Correction fluid	55
April 22: Envelops	22
April 25: Postage stamps	30
April 29: Detergent	87

Required: Prepare a petty cash book

- 20 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM
MID SEMESTER EXAMINATION – AUGUST 2021
RM 16 - MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark*

QUESTION ONE

Madam Mercy is a Unit Manager of Labour Ward. She is not satisfied with the way things are going in her department She decides adopt Situational leadership style in managing the Department.

- a. Define Situational leadership style - 2 marks
- b. Explain five (5) advantages of Situational leadership style - 5 marks
- c. Enumerate Six (6) other types of Leadership styles - 3 marks
- d. Explain the techniques Madam Mercy will use in solving problems in her Department - 10 marks

QUESTION TWO

As a Midwife, you recently took over a new role as the Manager of Maternity Ward. With a high level of commitment and motivation though new in the hospital, you ensure that processes and procedures and other resources are used in an efficient and effective manner. The ward has a bed capacity of 24 with 7 newly posted midwives.

Describe Ward Management under the following:

- a. Management of newly posted midwives - 5 marks
- b. Management of client care - 5 marks
- c. Management of the environment - 5 marks
- d. Management of supplies and equipment - 5 marks

Please Turn Over

QUESTION THREE

FINANCE

- a. As a Matron of Mother 2 Mothers Hospital, Donkorkrom a workshop was organized dubbed the essence of 'Time Value of Money' for individuals and corporates institutions. You participated and learnt that, for the most part of an organization, borrowing and investment are critical areas to watch out given your available resource. It was also understood that if one has to find out future value of any present sum of money, the technique of compounding is to be used and if the present value of any future sum is to be calculated, then the technique of discounting is used.

Required;

- i. State and explain the THREE (3) basic financial decisions in financial management. - 6marks
- ii. State any FOUR (4) objectives of financial management - 4 marks

- b. Given the level of Knowledge acquired from this workshop and by the use of Time value of money compounding formulas; Calculate NB (*marks would be awarded for show workings*)
 - i. Your Institution (M2M) wants to have GHS 20 million as a retirement package for its staff in 35 years. And you invested in a mutual fund paying an average of 18.75% interest each year compounded weekly. How much will your institution deposit into the mutual fund? - 2marks
 - ii. If your institution (M2M) had a choice of choosing GHS 3,000 now or GHS 5,000 in five years, which one would you choose for the institution if the annual interest rate were 12%? - 4 marks
 - iii. If M2M has a GHS 100,000 investment in T Bills with a 7% interest rate, compounded annually, how much will M2M have in 8 years? - 2 marks
 - iv. With quarterly compounding at 10% for 30 years, the future value of an initial investment of GHS 2,000 is closes to? - 2 marks

BEFORE YOU LEARN TO CARE,
YOU MUST CARE TO LEARN.

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM
MID SEMESTER EXAMINATION – AUGUST 2021
PBM 3 - MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1HR.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers

Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract

Question One

Madam Manu is a Senior Midwife at Choitram Hospital in the Western Region and head of her department. Last year, she won an award for her department as a result of effective Team work.

- a. Define Team work - 2 marks
- b. Enumerate **five (5)** importance of Team work - 5 marks
- c. State **five (5)** characteristics of a good team leader - 5 marks
- d. Explain **EIGHT (8)** factors that can impede effective team work - 8 marks

Question Two

FINANCE

- a. As a Matron of Mother 2 Mothers Hospital, Donkorkrom a workshop was organized dubbed the essence of 'Time Value of Money' for individuals and corporates institutions. You participated and learnt that, for the most part of an organization, borrowing and investment are critical areas to watch out given your available resource. It was also understood that if one has to find out future value of any present sum of money, the technique of compounding is to be used and if the present value of any future sum is to be calculated, then the technique of discounting is used.

Required;

- i. State and explain the **THREE (3)** basic financial decisions in financial management. - **6marks**
- ii. State any **FOUR (4)** objectives of financial management - **4 marks**
- b. Given the level of Knowledge acquired from this workshop and by the use of Time value of money compounding formulas; Calculate NB (marks would be awarded for show workings)
 - i. Your Institution (M2M) wants to have GHS 20 million as a retirement package for its staff in 35 years. And you invested in a mutual fund paying an average of 18.75% interest each year compounded weekly. How much will your institution deposit into the mutual fund? - **2marks**
 - ii. If your institution (M2M) had a choice of choosing GHS 3,000 now or GHS 5,000 in five years, which one would you choose for the institution if the annual interest rate were 12%? - **4 marks**
 - iii. If M2M has a GHS 100,000 investment in T Bills with a 7% interest rate, compounded annually, how much will M2M have in 8 years? - **2 marks**
 - iv. With quarterly compounding at 10% for 30 years, the future value of an initial investment of GHS 2,000 is closest to? - **2 marks**